

IN SILICO 0D MODEL FOR THE BEST PEEP SELECTION DURING MECHANICAL VENTILATION: RECRUITMENT VS RISK OF VILI

A. Formaggio^{1,2}, M. De Luca^{1,2}, G. Putame^{1,2}, S. Borrelli^{1,2}, A. L. Audenino^{1,2} and M. Terzini^{1,2}

1. Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Politecnico di Torino, Torino (Italy)

2. Polito^{BIO}Med Lab, Politecnico di Torino, Torino (Italy)

Introduction

Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy, widely used during the COVID-19 pandemic, is a mechanical ventilation (MV) approach to treat patient with hypoxemic respiratory failure. The positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) generation promotes the recruitment of non-aerated alveoli, improving lung compliance and oxygen saturation (SpO₂). On the other hand, the PEEP produces an overdistention of aerated alveoli, that can lead to ventilation-induced lung injury (VILI). In this study, an *in silico* model was developed to analyse the effect of different PEEP levels on the patient's lung, with the aim of selecting the best PEEP.

Methods

The patient and the ventilation systems were replicated as a 0D model (Fig. 1) in Simscape (Mathworks).

Figure 1: Schematics of the patient model

Two conditions were evaluated, one involving external MV of a patient in apnoea, and the other involving treatment of the patient during spontaneous breath, imposing various PEEP levels at the airway entrance. The recruitment of non-aerated alveoli occurs when the alveolar pressure rises above P_{rec} (in cyan, Fig. 2A), increasing the total lung compliance. The opposite mechanism occurs when the alveolar pressure drops below P_{col} (in blue, Fig. 2A). The risk of VILI (RoV) was estimated by calculating the power transmitted to the alveoli, based on *in vitro* data [1]. Eq. (1) is used to determine the partial pressure of alveolar O₂ ($P_{A}O_2$), relying on alveolar ventilation (\dot{V}_A) and O₂ metabolism ($\dot{V}O_2$) [2]. Using Eqs. (2) and (3), the SpO₂ is computed considering the alveolar collapse (col) and the ventilation-perfusion ratio (Ar) [3]. To validate the model, the ventilation systems were assembled *in vitro* and connected to a lung simulator (TestChest® V3).

$$P_{A}O_2 = (P_{atm} - P_{H_2O})(F_{iO_2} - \dot{V}O_2 / \dot{V}_A) \quad (1)$$

$$P_{a}O_2 = P_v O_2 \cdot col \cdot Ar + P_{A}O_2 \cdot \tau (1 - col \cdot Ar) \quad (2)$$

$$SpO_2 = \left(\frac{23400}{P_{a}O_2^3 + 150 \cdot P_{a}O_2} + 1 \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Results

The validation process produced optimal consistency between the 0D model and *in vitro* tests, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.9 to 1. The *in silico* model allowed to capture the lung mechanical behaviour (non-linear, hysteresis) and the dynamics of the alveolar recruitment during MV (Fig. 2). For the simulated patient, PEEP at 8 cmH₂O produced the highest therapy efficacy (ΔV_{eff}), while 10 cmH₂O maximized lung ventilation (ΔV_t) (Tab. 1). Both PEEP levels similarly enhanced SpO₂; therefore, 8 cmH₂O was chosen as the best PEEP, reflecting a lower RoV.

Figure 2: Pressure-Volume and Time-Volume curves for passive (A) and active (B) patients.

PEEP level (cmH ₂ O)	ΔV_{eff} (%)	ΔV_t (%)	SpO ₂ (%)	RoV (%)
4	0	-11.9	81.9	0.40
6	50.3	8.4	92.8	0.64
8	54.1	21.9	96.3	0.99
10	50.9	23.3	96.6	1.30
12	47.8	21.7	96.5	1.61

Table 1: Comparison of the PEEP levels effect.

Discussion

This study introduces a novel *in silico* 0D model able to analyse the effect of CPAP therapy on aerated (overdistention) and collapsed alveoli (recruitment) separately, predicting the RoV, and estimating the most effective PEEP level for the patient. Moreover, the high computational efficiency of the lumped elements, the flexibility to replicate various ventilation systems and patients, and the reliability, make the *in silico* 0D model a viable tool for clinical application.

References

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